

CO₂ SMOS

Solutions for a circular biobased industry

Research & Results

This booklet presents the work and achievements of Work Packages (WPs) 2-5 of the CO2SMOS project. WPs are structured sections of the project that break down the work into manageable parts. WPs 2-5 are CO2SMOS's technical WPs, focusing on scientific research, technological development, and innovation. They involve experiments, new technology development, and research outputs. Horizontal WPs, covering management, communication, impact, and ethics, are not included in this booklet.

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Contents

About the Project.....	pg 1
WP2: Primary conversion of CO ₂ into Bio-acetate and green syngas.....	pg 2
WP3: CO ₂ -Derived Intermediates and Monomers.....	pg 5
WP4: Scale-up of CO ₂ SMOS' Value Chains.....	pg 9
WP5: Transforming Biogenic CO ₂ into High-Value Biomaterials.....	pg 13

About the Project

The overall idea of the CO₂SMOS project is to develop a platform of innovative and cost-competitive technologies that transform bio-based industrial CO₂ emissions and renewable sources (green hydrogen and biomass) into added-value bioproducts: durable polymers, renewable biochemicals and biodegradable materials. With these compounds, it is possible to produce greener end-products such as packaging, coatings, and textiles.

Objectives

Develop breakthrough technologies for the conversion of CO₂ into high added-value chemicals. Define targets to reduce the energy requirements and production costs of the conversion process.

Design an integrated process that help bio-based industries to achieve zero or even negative GHG emissions, while boosting their competitiveness.

Process

The goal of the CO₂SMOS project is to develop a toolbox of 5 innovative technologies for bio-based industries to recycle their carbon emissions. Two primary conversion technologies transforms the CO₂ into bulk chemicals: bio-acetate and syngas. The 3 final conversion technologies transform these simple chemicals into more complex products with various industrial applications: polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA, PHB), 2,3-butanediol, long chain dicarboxylic acids C16-C18, BTEX, cyclic carbonates and hydroxycarboxylic acids.

WP2: Primary conversion of CO₂ into Bio-acetate and green syngas

The main objective was to develop innovative lab-scale solutions for converting biogenic CO₂ emissions into acetate and syngas—intermediate chemicals used in the production of CO₂SMOS end products. The solution can be divided into two parts based on the deployed technologies and targeted intermediates. On one hand, biological fermentation processes focus on producing bio-acetate from either CO₂/H₂ mixtures or syngas. On the other hand, electrocatalytic conversion of CO₂/H₂O into green syngas and value-added chemicals is carried out in an eCMR integrating an HT-PEM, an RWGS catalyst, and a water extraction membrane.

1. Biological Processes

- Advanced GMO preparation for gas (CO₂/CO/H₂) fermentation process.
- Optimisation of CO₂+H₂ and syngas fermentation process parameters for acetate production.

Two different strains were tested at lab scale for the production of acetate from CO₂ streams; CARTIF tested *Acetobacterium woodii* using CO₂/H₂ whereas BBEPP tried *Moorella thermoacetica* using syngas and CO₂/H₂. The fermentation with the later microorganism resulted in the most optimised process and consequently, it was the one that was scaled up within WP4.

For that purpose, a cross-flow microfiltration unit was installed in the bioreactor setup to allow a continuous and simultaneous production and extraction of acetate, thereby yielding cell-free broth containing acetate from syngas.

Key Outcomes

- Bio-acetate was effectively produced from CO_2/H_2 mixtures using wild type acetogenic bacteria *A. woodii*, and from $\text{CO}/\text{H}_2/\text{CO}_2$ mixtures using the acetogenic bacteria *Moorella thermoacetica*. Higher titers were achieved for *M. thermoacetica*.
- The production of acetate is favoured by a moderate increase in pressure.
- The gas fermentation process was scaled to a 10 L bioreactor using a continuous operation mode with cell-recycle.
- Results achieved in this task (Targets: 30 g/L acetate, 0.55 g/L/h):
 - ▶ Maximal acetate concentration of 17.8 g/L
 - ▶ Maximal acetate concentration of 17.8 g/L

These values were further improved, meeting the targets in WP4.

Schematic representation of a continuous fermentation process with cell recycle (created with BioRender.com)

10 L bioreactor equipped with peristaltic pumps, a ceramic filter, and additional vessels for continuous operation with cell-recycle at BBEP

2. Electrocatalytic processes

- Development of a high temperature PEM water electrolyser (HT-PEM) based on phosphoric acid doped PBI membranes operating at temperature from 140 to 180 °C.
 - ▶ Doping protocol developed for two commercial PBI membranes.
 - ▶ Optimisation of the electrolysis cell design and test conditions.
- Design, synthesis and characterisation of a catalyst for the reverse water gas shift (RWGS) reaction at low temperature to produce syngas.
- Design of a thin film polymeric membrane for the water extraction from the reaction chamber.

Illustration of different configurations of the CO₂SMOS reactor: fully integrated (upper scheme)

Key Outcomes

- Understanding of the constraints associated with PBI membranes.
- HT-PEM water electrolysis testing module for 25 cm² active area.
- Optimised Cu-based catalyst has shown good performance at temperatures lower than 300 °C.
- Development of a catalytic kinetic model.
- Manufacturing of defect free thin film polymeric membranes based in polyimide material (6FDA-6FpDA).

WP3: CO₂-Derived Intermediates and Monomers

WP3 focuses on producing CO₂-derived intermediates and monomers through biological and physicochemical processes. The biological component involves optimising fermentation techniques, while the physicochemical part develops extraction and purification methods.

1. Biological Processes

A. Fermentation steps

1. Anaerobic Fermentation:

- 2,3-butanediol (2,3-BDO): *Clostridium* strains were used to transform syngas (CO₂, CO, H₂) into 2,3-BDO, a key polymer precursor, optimised at lab scale.

2. Aerobic Fermentation:

- Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA): *Cupriavidus necator* and *Pseudomonas putida* were used to produce short-chain-PHA (0.66 g/L/h productivity) and medium-chain-PHA (0.11 g/L/h productivity), respectively, using diluted CO₂-derived acetate streams (WP2).
- 2,3-BDO: Recombinant *Escherichia coli* strains were used to produce meso-2,3-BDO (0.33 g/L/h productivity from glucose).
- LcDCA (Long-Chain Dicarboxylic Acids): Recombinant *Yarrowia lipolytica* cells cultured in CO₂-derived acetate streams (3.2 g/L/h biomass productivity) were used to produce LcDCA using C14 fatty acid supplementation in resting cell assays (0.461 g/L LcDCA production).

Goal: Lab scale development of 4 acetate conversion fermentation processes

B. Downstream steps:

1. PHB extraction:

High-purity PHB was isolated via enzymatic digestion and centrifugation, yielding 92.3% pure PHB from *C. necator*.

2. 2,3-BDO recovery:

An Aqueous Two-Phase Extraction (ATPE) system recovered 81% of 2,3-BDO in synthetic media. Scale-up trials showed 54% overall 2,3-BDO yield in real broths.

2. Physicochemical Processes

2.1 Catalytic processes: syngas to aromatics

WP3 also was devoted to produce BTEX and PX (benzene, toluene, Ethylbenzene, and Xylenes, in particular para-xylene) from the CO₂-derived syngas made in WP2. The work was divided into the development of a catalyst for the syngas to aromatics (StA) reaction and a solid electrolyte oxygen separator (from the reaction water subproduct) to shift the thermodynamic equilibrium of the reaction and promote the BTEX and PX yield.

A. StA reaction

H-ZSM-5 Zeolite with Si/Al ratio of 31 displayed selectivity to total aromatics (72.8% in hydrocarbons), while a modification of this catalyst showed the highest BTX and PX selectivity (BTX/aromatics = 66.5%, PX/aromatics = 38.7%, PX/xylenes = 71.8%).

B. SEOS materials design

Several materials have been selected or designed for the oxygen separator. As the main constrain for a ceramic electrochemical reactor is the operation temperature of the StA reaction, the materials are quite restricted.

- 1. Electrolyte: Scandia stabilised zirconia has been selected as the material of choice. Tests on BiVO_x-based materials have shown good oxygen transport, but low stability in reaction operation conditions.
- 2. Cathode: CGO/Cu composite electrode demonstrated activity for the water splitting at 450 °C.
- 3. Anode: Perovskite La_{0.2175}Pr_{0.217}Ba_{0.14}Sr_{0.4}Fe_{0.8}Co_{0.2}O_{3-δ}.

Key Outcomes

- Successful development of StA catalyst.
- Design and selection of electrochemical cell materials able to work at intermediate temperatures (400-450 °C).
- Development of a first button cell conforming a solid electrolyte oxygen separator (SEOS) electrochemical reactor and identification of optimisation points.

3. Organic/biocatalysed conversion to cyclic carbonates

In this part of WP3, a thermocatalytic process was developed for the conversion of CO₂ into cyclic carbonates, as these can be used as building blocks in the synthesis of 100% biological polymers such as polycarbonates or polyurethanes. The work was divided into development and characterisation of catalysts and lab-scale testing of the process conditions for the conversion of CO₂ to cyclic carbonates.

A. Development and characterization of catalysts

A series of crosslinked aromatic polymers were synthesised successfully both by solvothermal and microwave methods. These polymers showed high thermal stability with decomposition temperatures above 400 °C and moderate surface areas. From these polymers were prepared a series of metal-complexes with different metals (Fe, Al, Zn and Co) where the loading of metal was mostly around 1,5% and where the preferred coordination metal resulted to be "Fe".

B. Lab-scale testing of the process conditions for the conversion of CO₂ to cyclic carbonates

The next step was to apply one of the best catalysts, COS-1 MW@FeCl₂, in the conversion of vegetable oil derivatives into cyclic carbonates (Fig. 1) which also showed good recyclability up to 5 cycles.

Conversion of CO₂ to bio-based cyclic carbonates

Key Outcomes

- Successful development of microbial strains for bioplastic and biochemical production.
- Scalable protocols for isolating PHB, PHA, 2,3-BDO, and LcDCAs that meet industrial specifications.
- ATPE demonstrated high efficiency for 2,3-BDO recovery, highlighting potential for industrial application.
- A catalyst has been successfully designed for the syngas to aromatics reaction.
- Appropriate component materials for a SEOS have been selected and tested in StA operation conditions.
- Several catalysts containing different metals have been successfully prepared for the conversion reaction of CO₂ to cyclic carbonates.
- The best resulting catalysts were those containing Fe, which also showed good recyclability.
- The results demonstrate the substantial effectiveness of these catalysts in transforming sustainable feedstocks into cyclic carbonates.

WP4: Scale-up of CO₂SMOS' Value Chains

WP4 is the core of the CO₂SMOS project, focused on scaling up the value chains developed in previous work packages. It aims to bridge the gap between lab-scale research and real-world implementation by validating processes at the pilot scale. Ultimately, WP4 seeks to produce sufficient quantities of CO₂-derived chemicals for validation in real applications within WP5.

1. Biological Value Chains

Anaerobic Fermentation

CO₂ to Acetic acid (AAc)

The biological conversion of CO₂ and H₂ to acetic acid utilising *M. thermoacetica* was scaled up to a 150 L bioreactor. A filtration module was installed and optimised to extract acetic acid and allow for continuous operation.

CO₂ to 2,3-butanediol (2,3-BDO)

Clostridium autoethanogenum was successfully cultivated at 150 L scale, indicating the scalability of the process.

Aerobic Fermentation and downstream purification

AAc to Polyhydroxyalkanoates (mcl-PHA and PHB)

Cupriavidus necator and *Pseudomonas putida* were used to produce PHB, and mcl-PHA respectively. Fermentation processes were scaled up to 30L and 150L scale.

Downstream purification (DSP) methods for both fermentation processes were scaled up using relevant industrial equipment.

Additionally, the real CO₂-based acetic acid stream was used to produce PHB. Since the acetate stream has a low concentration, a continuous set-up at 30L and 150L scale was installed to feed, while keeping the PHB-accumulating biomass inside the reactor vessel, resulting in high PHB titers.

AAc to 2,3-BDO

2,3 BDO production using metabolically engineered *E. coli* was scaled up to 30 L. Acetic acid was used as feedstock during growth and glucose was used during production. A DSP method was developed resulting in a high purity 2,3-BDO end product.

Key Outcomes

- Continuous CO₂-based acetic acid production was achieved under stable conditions for > 20 days, producing multiple Kgs of CO₂-based acetic acid for subsequent biological conversion to PHB, PHA, and 2,3-BDO.
- Mcl-PHA production and DSP were achieved at a 150L scale. With a titer of > 30 g/L and high productivity, the KPIs and current SoTa were surpassed. After DSP, a PHA purity of > 98% was achieved and the pure polymer was used in WP5 for the production of stretch films.
- A setup with a circulation loop including a microfiltration unit was built at BBEPP and the CO₂-based acetic acid was successfully used by *C. necator* to grow and produce PHB. The process was further optimised resulting in 75 g/L PHB. After DSP, a couple of Kgs of high-purity PHB were sent to the partners in WP5 for application testing.

2. Electrochemical value chains

Syngas to BTEX and PX

Scale up an electrocatalytic cell for converting syngas ($\text{CO} + \text{H}_2$) into BTEX (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylenes) and PX (para-xylene) while integrating a membrane to selectively separate oxygen generated from water byproduct splitting.

- Selection of materials working at 400-450 °C and optimisation of cell configuration and fabrication.
- Electrochemical characterisation of the cell in SOFC and SOEC mode. Test of oxygen pumping.
- Syngas to BTEX reaction performed by using a catalyst developed in WP3.

HT-PEM water electrolysis

Development of a high-temperature PEM water electrolyser (HT-PEM) based on phosphoric acid-doped PBI membranes operating at temperatures from 120 to 140 °C.

- Degradation mechanism of the PBI electrolysis cell studied.

CO₂ to cyclic carbonates

Avantium has validated the thermocatalytic conversion of CO_2 to cyclic carbonates at (mini)-pilot scale from Epoxidized Soy Bean oil (ESBO) derived from biomass and using the catalyst developed by Funditec.

The results at small scale (1-5 ml substrate) were used as a basis by Avantium to develop a process at larger scale (~80 ml substrate in a 650 ml reactor). After optimisation, a ~90% conversion was achieved towards the cyclic carbonate soybean oil product and enough material was provided to Novamont to be used as CO_2 - and bio-based plasticiser for their biobased plastics formulations.

Key Outcomes

- An operational cell could be developed to work at temperatures as low as 400 °C. The cell performance is limited. Therefore, the fabrication of the cell needs further optimization and a readjustment of the operation parameters to produce BTEX in an electrochemical reactor.
- Sputtering optimisation of $\text{Ce}_{0.9}\text{Gd}_{0.1}\text{O}_{2-\delta}$ (CGO) layers to protect the electrolyte from reacting with the electrodes.
- Screen printing for electrode attachment.
- Increase lifetime of PBI electrolysis cell, from few hours reported in literature, up to 90h by decreasing the temperature of operation or reducing the potential. (scientific publication in preparation).
- Successful production of cyclic carbonates with promising plasticiser properties for bio-based plastics, using CO_2 and renewable substrates instead of fossil resources.
- Recyclability of the catalyst has been proven; the recycled catalysts have similar activity as fresh catalyst.

WP5: Transforming Biogenic CO₂ into High-Value Biomaterials

1. Novamont

Novamont, within the CO₂SMOS project, participated as an experienced end user responsible for validating the intermediate building blocks derived from CO₂ by CO₂SMOS partners. Using its proprietary technologies, Novamont converts these raw materials into innovative biodegradable and bio-based polyesters and biomaterials.

One notable result achieved is related to the use of PHA from BBEPF as raw material in the production of biomaterial for compostable film packaging. The compostable films derived from PHA exhibit excellent melt thermal stability (ASTM D444), and their rheological properties have been finely tuned to be compatible with film-blowing processes, a consolidated industrial technology in packaging manufacturing. Internal test was conducted that confirmed that these films meet stringent biodegradability standards (ISO 17556) and are compatible with certifications such as OK Compost, affirming that they biodegrade completely without leaving harmful residues. Mechanical testing (ASTM D882) shows that these films possess properties comparable to conventional packaging materials, making them a viable, sustainable alternative for both transparent packaging (such as lids) and opaque films used in organic waste collection.

In another application, PHA from biogenic CO₂ are used as raw materials in the production of biomaterials to create fully recyclable and biodegradable injection moulded prototypes, such as grow pots.

Transparent and compostable film for packaging (1) and 100% RECYCLABLE and biodegradable biomaterial for injection moulding (2), both including CO₂SMOS PHA.

Parallel to the PHA developments, Novamont has also focused on validating SBOC as plasticisers of novel biomaterial grades in two different technologies: injection moulding and film blowing. These materials exhibit regular processability and display distinctive rheological characteristics, including effective plastification and compatibilisation behaviour (ASTM D4440).

Biodegradable and compostable biomaterial for injection moulding comprising SBOC from CO2SMOS.

2. Avantium

Avantium has been working on novel polyesters as sustainable materials for the future. It has demonstrated that the monomers sourced from the Project can be used to produce materials with significantly improved properties compared to a material like PET and PETG, such as temperature resistance. Indeed, by improving the glass transition temperature (T_g), the novel polyesters by Avantium are designed to withstand, for instance, boiling water.

This was achieved starting from 2,3-BDO used as diol and terephthalic acid in the synthesis of novel polyesters. Avantium has developed a number of novel and scalable strategies to overcome challenges such as the low reactivity of 2,3-BDO. Amongst the main results achieved by Avantium: an amorphous polyester composed solely of terephthalate and 2,3-BDO with $T_g > 100^\circ\text{C}$. Additionally, a new synthesis technique aimed at recycling PET was proven by combining CO2SMOS 2,3-BDO with actual waste packaging R-PET to create a copolyester with increased T_g . This highlights the potential of using bio-based and CO_2 -based products in developing high-performance materials.

3. Nadir

Nadir, thanks to its knowledge in development of custom materials for 3D printing, focused its activities on evaluation of the exploitability, as feedstock for Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) process, of the biomaterials derived from biogenic CO_2 .

The process to convert these polymeric compounds to filaments have been improved and extensively tested to verify the printability of the novel materials.

Process Flow Diagram: from plastic pellets to printed test samples.

A first group of materials that have been tested contained PHA from the Project and were characterised by a wide printing window temperature (175°C-220°C), low tendency to stringing, high layer adhesion and pleasant opaque appearance. A second group of materials including up to 20% of PHB from CO2SMOS technologies were successfully converted in filaments for 3d printing by NADIR. These materials are characterised by enhanced flexibility and biodegradability and they are printable at lower temperature (175°C- 200 °C). Finally, a special compound based on the previous blends PLA/PHB and containing hydroxyapatite (HA) has been developed and tested for application in tissue engineering research field as alternative of compound based on PLA/HA. The addition of the biocompatible polymer PHB to PLA/HA blend increases the processability of the compound and permits to maintain the required flexibility of the filament making it possible to meet the demand of the market for products with higher HA content (up to 35%).

Reels containing filaments based on PLA/PHB/ blend and the 3D printed test samples made with the same materials

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